

Teacher- Parent Interactions: Discovering Full Accomplishments In Language Learning Environments Through Parental Involvement Among Iraqi Efl Teenagers

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Abstract

This study was conducted to find out Teacher- Parent interactions and discover full accomplishments in Language Learning environments through parental involvement among Iraqi EFL Teenagers. This was accomplished with two groups of participants during a multi-stage process. In the first stage, data were gathered on ten young learners with an age range of six to ten years' old who were studying English in the elementary levels in a language institute in Bagdad, Iraq. The following instruments/data collection tools were used: a) To respond to the first three research questions, teacher's field notes were used within a case study framework over some selected young learners. b) To response to the last question, among the second group of the participants- adolescents- a modified version of Taylor's Quadripolar Model of Identity (TQMI) questionnaire was administered. Aliakbari and Amiri (2018) had validated the scales of this questionnaire among Iraqi students as EFL learners. The researcher relied on TQMI in an Iraqi context among 930 adult learners. They reported good indices of Chronbach alpha all above .08. The findings portrayed that teachers' achievements improved on many accounts such as being familiar with students' aims and personal attitudes to the extent that the researcher can engage them in the learning process.

Introduction

For language learning, the psychological and behavioral aspects of learning are regarded of the paramount importance and require to be clearly and obviously discussed. According to Schunk (2012), people disagree about the precise nature of learning, since there is no one definition of learning that is generally accepted by theorists. Some define learning as "an enduring change in behavior, or in the capacity to behave in a given fashion, which results from practice or other forms of experience" (Schunk, 2012, p.3). Therefore, assess learning based on the three criteria: One criterion is that "learning involves change"—in behavior or in the capacity for behavior. People learn when they become capable of doing something differently. At the same time, we must remember that learning is inferential. Learning is not perceivable directly but rather its products or outcomes. The second criterion is that "Learning endures over time". Thirdly, "learning occurs through experience" (e.g., practice, observation of others).

Regarding the above definition of "learning" and "behavior" in learning process, the role of the parents as a catalyzer or speed-up agent should be mentioned and discussed. According to Sahagun (2015), both parents and teachers expect certain things to happen. For example, parents expect teachers to train their students and to guide their learning so they can have success. Second, he regards communication as a two-way street; for example, when a child comes to school and they are well groomed and well rested and their homework is completed, a teacher presumes that the parent/caregiver is involved in the process of helping so that the child is successful and prepared. Finally, based on Sahagun's suggestion, the third one is realization that is meant when both a child and a parent feel supported by the teacher and vice versa, students will have a greater advantage in their ability to be successful when there is a mutual understanding on the part of the teachers and the parents.

When families and schools work together, students benefit emotionally, academically, and behaviorally (Adamski, Fraser, & Peiro, 2013). Students whose families are engaged in school activities enjoy more than students whose parents are disconnected from school (Adamski et al, 2013).

Negative home-school relationships have an opposite effect. Poor parent-teacher relationship exerts a strong negative influence on teachers' ratings of students' behavior; poor parent-teacher relationship, on the other hand, may even supersede students' behavioral history (Serpell & Mashburn, 2011). Throughout this study, the researcher is going to document the issues involved in learning English as a foreign language through parental involvement to increase more achievement.

Statement of the Problem

Unfortunately, there are some parents who are unfair and they forget that the teacher has to deal with thirty five or forty students in one session in a classroom. There are parents, at the other end of the spectrum, who may often prove to be more of a concern for teachers. The challenge for teachers in English language teaching programs is how to make positive connections with parents. When teachers and parents work together, they can support children and, as a team, help children reach their potential. The opposite can also happen when both parties are at cross-purposes.

the researcher documented the issues involved in learning English as a foreign language through parental involvement to increase more achievement. According to Finders and Lewis (1994), children who do not succeed in language learning have parents who are usually not involved in educational activities or support the goals at home). At the same time, lack of participation among parents of socially and culturally diverse students is also well documented (Clark 1983; Delgado-Gaitan, 1991). So in order to be successful in foreign language learning, it seems that parental involvement is totally needed. This study tries to show the importance of parents and teachers' connection as to language learning in an Iraqi context.

The Objective of the Study

This study attempts to discover different reasons behind lack of parental involvement in language teaching context, a topic that has obtained less attention on the part of language scholars. For many parents, their own individual school experiences may bring about obstacles to their involvement. Nevertheless, parents who have left the schools and have a weak relation do not feel confident in school settings (Comer, 1984). Also, many classroom teachers feel unprepared to work with families who speak limited English or no English at all. Consequently, teachers are required to help knowing that schools are accountable for the achievement of these students. For instance, English language teachers must learn how to reach out to parents in order to become more involved with teachers.

Parents-teachers connection and success in English language learning among 5-to10-year-old male and female English language learners as well as adolescence with an age range of 12 to 16. But, the researcher thinks that the same research can be done on other age groups and the results of that research would complete the results of this study.

Research Questions

The following questions are the foci of the current study:

Q.1. To what extent an active interaction between/among teachers and parents can effective on young learners' overall achievements within Iraqi English language classrooms at private language schools?

Q.2. What are the Iraqi EFL teachers' expectations from parents about young language learners?

Q.3 Based on the teachers' attitudes, what problems are involved in engaging more parental aids for language education in Iraqi educational contexts with younger learners?

Q.4. What are older learners' (adolescents) perceptions of learning English with regard to four relational contexts including language learners' family members, classmates, teachers and best friends? Can gender interact in the process?

2. Review of the Related Literature

"The human's common sense requires that getting parents involved in their children's education is a good option" (Lynne, 1998, p. 5). Traditionally, parents thought that teachers and schools are the only responsible agents for their children's education and training. Through such links with the parents, the teacher must enlighten the parents on the physical, spiritual, mental, and emotional development of the child. The parents wish to feel reassured that the teacher values the child and is concerned about him/her, and that the teacher needs their support for the successful performance of the child at school. The parents do not want to perceive the teacher as someone who accuses, judges, or influences their children. It is very important to communicate properly with the child, expecting responsible behavior from him/her at home and at school, and consistently ensure that he/she abides by the rules.

Parents and teachers should make efforts to create a suitable learning environment for children. The first learning experience acquired by the child at home should support the efforts to learn at school. This was thought to increase the success rate of the teacher in his/her class applications (Burns, Roe, & Ross, 1992). Nunan (2003), Enever and Moon (2009) point out all that parents are behind the push for English to be taught to children at earlier and earlier ages, without going into any details as to what that means for home-school partnerships.

According to Linse (2011), parent involvement has been positively related to children's educational performance. Parent-home involvement was also assessed based on how the parents reported managing their children's time, talking about school topics, and helping with their homework. Besides, they give account of the level of their involvement in their child's literacy for example, how often they limit TV time and how often

they encouraged/told their children to do non-homework reading in order to improve their general knowledge. The final point of evaluation was parent expectations of the students. However, the results showed that poverty, race/ethnicity, parent education, and parent involvement played a significant role in their student's achievement and regarded as influential factors in the students' education.

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Assigning homework designed by teacher to increase student-parent interactions, holding workshops for families, and communicating with parents about their children's education and their strength and weaknesses in the learning process and reports them back to their parents for more investigation were the specific practices that could forecast the level of parental engagements.

Quezada (2010) state that parental engagement create different positive outcomes for the whole family, such as improved behavior and attitudes toward school, positive parent-child relationship, improved parental involvement, self-confidence and expertise, increased language achievement, and students' cognitive growth. However, these are considered as significant factors for Iraqi families. Also the probability of the level of involvement being sustained over time is dependent upon how they understand themselves as leaders and harness in their children's education's education process (Emerson, 2012).

Dempsey and Sandler (1995) provided a theoretical definition for researching about parental engagement in the teaching process. In fact, their theoretical model defines parental involvement based on three main points: (1) why parents become involved in their children's education, (2) how parents choose specific types of involvement, and (3) why parental engagement has a positive influence on students' educational results. On the other hand, according to Fan and Chen (2001), this theoretical basis "is going to be more than a typology for parent engagement, since it not only deals with a certain types of parent engagement, but more significantly, it tries to clarify why parents select to get engaged in their children's process, and what instruments are through which parent association apply positive effect on students' educational results." (p.3)

Parental involvement has many obstacles and hindrances an important obstacle that obstructs the teachers' way for active involvement in their children's education is teachers' attitudes and family resources. For example, teacher opinions about the effect of their efforts about teacher's participation parents in students' learning in order to foresee their efforts to encourage family involvement and bringing them to school environment.

families in which the parent work full-time, where the family is a type of large-number one, or where English is not spoken or read well, these items can be regarded as likely barriers and significant barriers to the teachers' participation in their children's education (Epstein, 1995, p.13-14).

Empirical studies on

Savacool (2011) investigated the likely hindrances to the parent participation and teacher-parent relations. The results showed that parental involvement influence children's achievement more than school procedures especially in the primary years. Besides, researchers also showed positive effects on children, families, and school when schools and parents continuously support and encourage a child's learning and development.

Likewise, in a study conducted by Psico Soma 2013 examined parental involvement in toddler's education, Guidelines for teacher. It was found that parent participation in education is of paramount importance besides, it is one of the big incentives for all children to learn; moreover, it is because the children, particularly those learner in the lower ages or primary levels, feel a sense of power on the part of their parent and they try to make their parents happy by perseverance and being successful in education.

Therefore, in another study investigated by Washington (2011) regarding parental involvements and its trends and effects on school learners, the impact of parental participation. However, the analyses on the trend and status of parental involvement showed that there was a statistically significant rise in parental involvement over the years.

Method

Participants and setting

The present study was accomplished with two groups of participants during a multi-stage process. In the first stage, data were gathered on some ten young learners with an age range of six to ten years' old who were studying English in the elementary levels in a language institute in in Bagdad, Iraq. In this stage, learners'

whose parents were much more involved in the learning processes were compared with those kids who did not have much parental provisions in terms of mainly their overall linguistic achievement and/or social support.

Table 3.1

Demographical information of the participants in the first stage

Participant No.	Age	Gender
Fatimeh	10	Female
Rabihe	10	Female
Soheib	6	Male
Sumi	8	Male
Raihane	9	Female
Ahmad	10	Male
Sami	10	Male
Fatemeh	6	Male
Roghayeh	6	Female
Hananeh	9	Female

The participants in the second group were selected from among both male and females from among Iraqi students in this study with some forty learners who were selected from among sixty adolescents with an age range of 12-16 year old studying in various language schools in city of Baghdad. This group of learners participated in filling a questionnaire on identity-based subjects with regard to relational contexts, which assessed their preferences for family supports as compared with three other important people in their surrounding such as their language teachers, best friends, and classmates. Table 3.2 below represents their demographical as well as educational information in their English course at this second stage.

Table 3.2

Demographical Information of the Participants in the Second Stage

<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>English knowledge at school (year)</i>	<i>English knowledge in language institutes (year)</i>	<i>Self-reported English grade level</i>
14.20	<i>Male (50%) Female (50%)</i>	2.34	2.84	<i>1-10 (0) 11-15 (2.6%) 16-20 (97.4%)</i>

Instrument

In order to handle this study, the following instruments/data collection tools were used:

1. To respond to the first three research questions, teacher's field notes were used within a case study framework over some selected young learners.

2. To response to the last two questions, among the second group of the participants- adolescents- a modified version of Taylor's Quadripolar Model of Identity (TQMI) questionnaire among highly referenced models for identity issues was administered. This questionnaire had first been developed and validated by Florentina Taylor (2011) in Nottingham (UK) and further validated by Bryman, (2008) and Cohen (2000) in order to help ESL students have a more rewarding time at school. However, in this study, it was first modified by the researcher to well suit the purposes of this study and measure the overall parental involvement of Iraqi participants among the adolescents as mapped with the effectiveness of their participation in their learning process development and their overall achievements in their school English courses.

Scales/subscales of the modified TQMI questionnaire in this study

No.	Self-system scales	System Subtypes	Items
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1.	Part I Motivational perceptions for Foreign language Learning	A. English teacher B. Classmates C. Best friends D. Family	1, 2, 3, 4
2.	Part II Imposed Selves	Present Future	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 7,8,9,10, 11, 12
3.	Part III Public Selves		1,2,3,4,5,6

For the purposes of this research, the modified version had three sections. In the first section, the Quadra system subtypes including 1) English teachers, 2) learners’ classmates, 3) best friends, and 4) their family were considered on how adolescents maintained their relation with them.

In the first section of the original questionnaire for this study, depending on some hypothesized dynamic relationships, it was thought that a person’s identity may be materialized in four main self-system categories such as the learner who is submissive, duplicitous, rebellious and harmonious, which according to the corroborated relationship between and among four selves (ideal, private, imposed and public), with diverse people, one may be placed into each category.

Participants were required to choose one of the relational contexts for each four diverse vignette. For example, the first vignette was:

“They completely know what kind of person I am. What they expect me to do in my life is different from what I would like to do, so , to this reason, I prefer to give up my intentions and do what they think is better for me. What they want me to do in life is more important than what I’d have liked, so I’ll do what they say”.

In this study, the rest of this questionnaire was modified to include only two selves namely public and imposed due to the status of English instructions in the context of Iran in which the English uses in the society is not primary. Accordingly, ideal and private selves had nearly no place.

The second section then catered for imposed selves within individuals on two time intervals (present and future) and finally the last section assessed the learners’ public selves. Students’ responses ranged from 1 (Never true of me/ very little/ very unimportant), to 6 (Always true of me, very much, very important).

For examining its appropriateness in terms of other concepts of validity and reliability issues, the researcher relied on Aliakbari and Amiri’s research (2018) which had validated TQMI in an Iraqi context among 930 adult learners. In their study, they reported good indices of Chronbach alpha all above .08 for public and imposed selves. In this study, as table 3.4 verifies, the Chronbach alpha among 38 respondents for the two intended selves among four groups (public vs. imposed) were estimated.

Table 3.4

Cronbach's alpha values for the L2 Quadripolar Identity Questionnaire in this study

Learning Perceptions	Public selves	Imposed selves
.53	.95	.94

Procedure

Choose two groups: young - kids’ group and older learners including some volunteering adolescents.

In the first stage, some ten young learners were chosen from one language school at Baghdad, Iraq. Therefore, the intention of the researcher of talking about Parental/other Support is that some of the parents are very cooperative and do not hesitate to waste time and any energy in advocating their children's development. The second group including their parents, best friends, classmates and language teachers, the adolescents were selected. The researcher administered the TQMI questionnaire- the modified and translated (Persian version) of this questionnaire- among the adolescents.

Results

Phase one: Teachers' Reflection on Action among Kid's Groups

-Mismatch between Teacher's and Parent's Literacy

In the processes of learning and through experiencing of getting involvement with Iraqi parents, I have usually attempted to involve their positive help. In this process, I faced with diverse problems such as low literacy of the majority of the parents in English language. In the following, I have mentioned some examples as in case reported by Rabihe a 10 years old girl who learns English at language institutes of Baghdad, Iraq and had a mother with lower level of education in English.

-Involvement with the Personal Life of my Students

Duaa's case was conspicuous in this regard. She was clever at the beginning but did not trust herself and had much more confidence in her peers. From the second semester, when Fatimeh, her play school classmate shared the same class with Duaa, I found out due to competition she had with Fatimeh, she was more involved, and wanted to work with her to dramatically improve in her lessons because Duaa asks mother to work with her every so often.

-Knowing the Students' Behavior at Home

Ahmad as a 6-year-old boy, who was so neat, orderly and obsessive-looking, was a case in point. His behaviors in the class annoyed her classmates and teacher in some cases. After I sustained talk with his mother, I found out that Ahmad had not been still ready to share his materials/toys with his classmates, so this had put him in trouble. After making lots of attempts to make friends with other classmates as his mother also insisted, it was interesting that at that time Ahmad no longer resisted and allowed Heidar to play with him after his mother told teacher mother sensitivities.

Phase Two: Adolescents' Groups

Table 4.1

Frequency counts/percent for the first vignette in the modified questionnaire

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	My English teachers	5	13.2	13.2	13.2
	My family members	25	65.8	65.8	78.9
	My classmates	2	5.3	5.3	84.2
	My best friends	2	5.3	5.3	89.5
	All	4	10.5	10.5	100.0
	Total	38	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.2

Gender and Relational Context Preferences by the Adolescents Group

Frequency Counts for item1

Total

		My English teachers	My family members	My classmates	My best friends	All	
Gender	female	3	11	2	2	1	19
	male	2	14	0	0	3	19
Total		5	25	2	2	4	38

As seen in table 4.2, within most rated category-family members- male adolescents had more tendency (14, 56%) towards connections/associations with family. In order to check if this was also statistically significant, a chi-square was run as seen in table 4.3 below.

Table 4.3
Chi-Square Tests for item 1

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.560 ^a	4	.235
Likelihood Ratio	7.154	4	.128
Linear-by-Linear Association	.021	1	.885
N of Valid Cases	38		

a. 8 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.00.

As shown in table 4.2, a chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between respondents' gender and relational contexts preferences in vignette 1. The relation between these variables was not significant, $X^2(2, N = 38) = .23, p. >.05$. Based on this table, gender could not have any influence over selected relational contexts as explicated in the first vignette.

The second vignette of the modified TQMI questionnaire assessed the same situation above with the order of adolescents' tendency towards giving ignorance on the part of four important others recounting adolescents as being duplicitous in their learning affairs:

Vignette 2:

They don't really know what sort of person I really am, and it's not important for me that they do. They would like me to do something else in life than I would, and that's why I'll pursue my own dreams without letting them know. At the same time, I'll give them the impression that I do what they ask me to, even though I'm actually seeing about my own business. I know better.

Initially, table 4.4 details descriptive statistics for this second item (vignette).

Table 4.4
Frequency Counts for Item2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	My English teachers	5	13.2	13.2	13.2
	My family members	3	7.9	7.9	21.1
	My classmates	21	55.3	55.3	76.3
	My best friends	7	18.4	18.4	94.7
	All	2	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	38	100.0	100.0	

As table 4.4 verifies, this time, the tendency for each categorized relational context including adolescents' English teachers, family members, classmates, and best friends, were assorted with "classmates" having the most rated cell (21, 55.3%). This could also verify how in comparison with classmates and best friends, inclination with giving ignorance is directed towards classmates among Iraqi learners.

In response to the second section of the questions as to the interaction of gender in this process, cell differences were again assessed (Tables 4.2 & 4.3).

Table 4.5

*Gender * item2 Cross tabulation*

Count		item2					all	Total
		My English teachers	My family members	My classmates	My best friends			
Gender	female	2	1	8	7	1	19	
	male	3	2	13	0	1	19	
Total		5	3	21	7	2	38	

According to 4.5 represents, male adolescents (13, 61.9%) had more tendency to show their ignorance of classmates towards their prospective future compared with female groups. More or less, affinity with classmates on the part of female learners could have possible interpretations in this regard, which showed this encountering was less highlighted with female students. However, in order to see if this was statistically significant, again another chi-square was run as seen in the following table 4.6.

Table 4.6

Chi-Square Tests for item 2

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.724 ^a	4	.068

Likelihood Ratio	11.447	4	.022
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.569	1	.109
N of Valid Cases	38		

a. 8 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.00.

As shown in 4.5, and subsequent chi-square test in table 4.6 for the test of independence to examine the relation between respondents' gender and relational contexts preferences in vignette 2, the results showed that relation between these variables was not significant, $X^2(2, N = 38) = .06, p > .05$. Based on this table, gender could not have any effect over selected relational contexts for the second vignette though with a border line effect ($p = .06$)

The third characterized situation- vignette 3- assessed respondents' tendency to follow their own goals in life although they acknowledged that they had tendency, but this inclination could not be actualized due to having a rebellious character. They believed in their own abilities to openly refuse any help since the directions were different. So, their perceived abilities to solve their own problems deterred them to be more submissive or duplicitous as in the first subsequent two cases above:

Vignette 3:

What they would like me to do in life is different from what I would like to do, so that's why I'll pursue my own dreams even if I have to rebel against them. They know me well, I haven't got anything to hide, and if they want to force me into doing something, I am likely to refuse it openly. What they want me to do is less important than what I want.

First, descriptive statistics for this item are represented in table 4.7 below.

Table 4.7

Frequency Counts for Item3

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	My English teachers	8	21.1	21.1	21.1
	My family members	10	26.3	26.3	47.4
	My classmates	9	23.7	23.7	71.1
	My best friends	8	21.1	21.1	92.1
	All	3	7.9	7.9	100.0
	Total	38	100.0	100.0	

Besides, according to table 4.7, the preferences for each categorized relational context including adolescents' English teachers, family members, classmates, and best friends, were again varied with "my family members" having the most rated cell (10, 26.3%). Here, this could somehow show that although in relation with family members, respondents had tendencies towards their family members, but in the majority of cases, they liked to free themselves from these restraints.

In response to the second section of the questions as to the interaction of gender in this process, cell differences were once more assessed in terms of meaningful significance (Tables 4.7 & 4.8

Table 4.7

*Gender * item3 Cross tabulation*

Count		Item3					Total
		My English teachers	My family members	My classmates	My best friends	all	
Gender	female	5	5	2	6	1	19
	male	3	5	7	2	2	19
Total		8	10	9	8	3	38

Table 4.8

Chi-Square Tests for item 3

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.611 ^a	4	.230
Likelihood Ratio	5.880	4	.208
Linear-by-Linear Association	.067	1	.796
N of Valid Cases	38		

a. 8 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.50.

As table 4.8 verifies, a chi-square test of independence was performed to examine the relation between respondents' gender and relational contexts preferences in vignette 3. The relation between these variables was not significant, $X^2(2, N = 38) = .23, p > .05$. Based on this table, gender could not have any effect over selected relational contexts as mapped on adolescents' groups having rebellious character in the third vignette. The last vignette represented a harmonious character in the presented situation:

Vignette 4:

Vignette: They know me very well and appreciate me for what I am. My dreams for the future are very similar to what they'd like me to do in life. They don't want to impose anything on me, but give me the total liberty to choose, and they always appreciate my decisions about my future. They help me feel really fulfilled.

Table 4.9 presents descriptive statistics for this last item.

Table 4.9

Frequency Counts for Item 4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid My English teachers	14	36.8	36.8	36.8

My family members	14	36.8	36.8	73.7
My classmates	2	5.3	5.3	78.9
My best friends	5	13.2	13.2	92.1
All	3	7.9	7.9	100.0
Total	38	100.0	100.0	

As table 4.9 confirms, the preferences for each categorized relational context including adolescents' English teachers, family members, classmates, and best friends, were assorted with two items "my family members" and "my teachers" having the same rated cell that stood in the equal rate (36.8%). This showed among other things that learners wanted to move along this idealized situation with a pleasant-sounding behavior towards language teachers and family member.

In response to the second section of the questions as to the interaction of gender in this process, cell differences were assessed in terms of meaningful significance (Tables 4.10 & 4.11).

Table 4.10

*Gender * item4 Cross tabulation*

Count		Item4					Total
		My English teachers	My family members	My classmates	My best friends	all	
Gender	Female	12	4	1	1	1	19
	Male	2	10	1	4	2	19
Total		14	14	2	5	3	38

Table 4.11

Chi-Square Tests for item 4

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.848 ^a	4	.019
Likelihood Ratio	12.849	4	.012
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.696	1	.017
N of Valid Cases	38		

a. 6 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.00.

Based on the results from table 4.11, it was seen that just in this case, the relation of the gender by highest rate happened about "Family Members" showing that the boys with keeping more relation with their family members were significantly and meaningfully thinking that their goals with family members on learning issues and their future job opportunities could be similarly achieved by having more connections with family members though girls thought that they should be more in line with their language teachers to achieve success in learning English as verified in abovementioned vignette (vignette 4).

The Second section of the questionnaire

The second section of the modified TQMI evaluated respondents' preferences towards achieving their goals in learning English as mapped on their two selves (Imposed and Public). Within imposed self as an identity framework in Taylor's work (2010), demonstrations represent other people's hopes, desires and expectations that an individual is supposed to achieve in the future. The scores that each respondent received in this section of the questionnaire (Items 1 through 12) were enumerated for each four social relational contexts in which the learners reflected functions including family members, language teachers, best friends and classmates. Table 4.12 represents descriptive statistics for the present imposed self-realizations (Items 1 through 6) as reflected in the respondents' views.

Table 4.12
Descriptive statistics for present imposed self on four relational contexts

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My English teacher	38	23.00	36.00	34.2895	3.08359
My classmate	38	10.00	36.00	24.0789	8.37106
My best friends	38	8.00	36.00	26.4474	8.43640
My family members	38	20.00	36.00	34.0263	3.52203
Valid N (listwise)	38				

As is clear in Table 4.12 from the statistics of the relational contexts, the level of imposing on the part of teachers and families on the learners was nearly the same and both had the same powers. This showed that regarding present imposed identity indices, compared with others, these two categories had more supremacies/concerns based on the learners' attitudes. Besides, other two case categories had the mean of 24.0789 and 26.4474 respectively. In order to differentiate the four mean scores of relational contexts, non-parametric Friedman Test for repeated measures was used. This was due to the detected non-normality in the data case as shown in table 4.13 for the SK test.

Table 4.13
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Present imposed teacher	Present imposed classmate	Present imposed best friends	Present imposed family members
N		38	38	38	38
Normal	Mean	34.2895	24.0789	26.4474	34.0263
Parameters ^{a,b}	Std. Deviation	3.08359	8.37106	8.43640	3.52203
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.328	.163	.189	.293
	Positive	.290	.124	.129	.288
	Negative	-.328	-.163	-.189	-.293
Test Statistic		.328	.163	.189	.293
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000 ^c	.013 ^c	.001 ^c	.000 ^c

The results from Friedman test are shown in tables 4.14 for the mean ranks and table 4.15 for the significance test as shown below.

Table 4.14
Ranks for Present imposed self

	Mean Rank
Teacher	3.39
Classmate	1.37

best friends	1.99
family members	3.25

Table 4.15
Friedman Test for present imposed self on four relational contexts
Test Statistics^a

N	38
Chi-Square	79.448
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

As seen in table 4.15, comparison of the repeated measures was performed using Friedman's test showing a statistically significant difference regarding four relational contexts, $\chi^2(3) = 79.448$, $p = .000 < 0.005$. This showed the preference of language teachers over the other three case categories.

In the next phase, the dataset was checked on future imposed self/identity. Table 4.16 shows the initial descriptive statistics.

Table 4. 16
Descriptive statistics for future imposed self on four relational contexts

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My English teacher	38	8.00	30.00	24.8684	6.19577
My classmates	38	5.00	30.00	18.9737	8.04879
My best friend	38	6.00	36.00	23.2105	9.62305
My family members	38	16.00	39.00	30.7632	6.31786
Valid N (listwise)	38				

As table 4.16 shows, among the four categories "the family members" had the most influence on the learners since the obtained mean equaled to 30.7632 which was the highest amount compared to other factors.

Again, in order to differentiate the four mean scores of relational contexts as mapped on future imposed self, another non-parametric Friedman Test for repeated measures was used (Table 4.18). This was due to the non-normality detected for two columns as shown in table 4.17.

Table 4.17
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

			Future imposed self/ teacher	Future imposed self /my classmates	Future imposed self/ best friend	Future imposed self/ family members
N			38	38	38	38
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean		24.8684	18.9737	23.2105	30.7632
	Std. Deviation		6.19577	8.04879	9.62305	6.31786
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute		.204	.136	.121	.196
	Positive		.204	.116	.092	.177
	Negative		-.193	-.136	-.121	-.196
Test Statistic		.204	.136	.121	.196	
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000 ^c	.073 ^c	.174 ^c	.001 ^c	

In the following, Table 4.18 presents the ranks and subsequent table 4.19 shows the results from Friedman test.

Table 4.18
Ranks for future imposed self

	Mean Rank
Teacher	2.39
My classmates	1.30
Best friend	2.51
Family members	3.79

Table 4.19
Friedman Test for future imposed self on four relational contexts
Test Statistics^a

N	38
Chi-Square	74.174
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Friedman Test

As understood from table 4.19, comparison of the repeated measures was performed using Friedman's test showing a statistically significant difference regarding four relational contexts for future imposed self, $\chi^2(3) = 74.174$, $p = .000 < 0.005$. This significantly showed the preference of family members (MR = 3.79) over the other two case categories.

The last section of the questionnaire showed the learners' partialities for public self as social representation of the learners in diverse contexts. Table 4.20 shows descriptive statistics for public self on four relational contexts.

Table 4. 20
Descriptive statistics for public self on four relational contexts

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
My English teacher	38	6.00	36.00	32.2632	6.37005
My classmates	38	6.00	36.00	23.5263	9.42606
My best friends	38	6.00	36.00	24.8684	9.69305

	38	6.00	36.00	32.7895	5.83632
My family members					
Valid N (listwise)	38				

Based on the statistics obtained from descriptive statistics for public self on four relational contexts it was quite clear that the mean for “family members (parental involvement) and the teacher was much more than the other two categories. Based on the mean of obtained data that equals to 32.7895, it is shown that the external agents as external motivator for learners are family and teachers and they have the most influence on the learning of the respondents. However, in order to check if this was statistically significant, another Friedman test was run (Tables 4. 21 & 4.22).

Ranks for public self on four relational contexts

	Mean Rank
Teacher	3.21
Classmates	1.55
best friends	1.96
family members	3.28

Table 4.22

Friedman Test for public self on four relational contexts

Test Statistics^a

N	38
Chi-Square	62.953
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a.

As clear from table 4.22, comparison of the repeated measures using Friedman’s test showed a statistically significant difference regarding four relational contexts for public self, $\chi^2(3) = 62.953$, $p = .000 < 0.005$. This significantly showed the preference of family members (MR = 3.28) over the other two case categories.

Discussion

The researcher attempted to make contact with the younger learners’ parents. Three themes were emerged in the first phase including 1) mismatch between teacher’s and parent’s literacy, 2) engagement with my students’ personal life, and 3) knowing the students’ behavior at home. In all, the researcher thinks this engagement among kid’s groups still had lots of other benefits, which helped a teacher to improve understanding of the complex behavior of learners.

For the adolescents’ groups, regarding four personality factors including being submissive, duplicitous, rebellious and harmonious, the preferences for each categorized relational context including adolescents’ English teachers, family members, classmates, and best friends were assorted with: 1) “my family members” was very vivid without any significant difference between girls and boys, 2) “My classmates” was very rich without any significant difference between girls and boys 3) “my family members” in the rebellious category again without significant difference between girls and boys, and finally, 4) “family members” and “language teachers” in the harmonious characterization. For this last category, the difference between male and female students was significant with males having more tendency towards family members and females towards language teachers.

Regarding the second section of the modified TQMI evaluated respondents' preferences towards achieving their goals in learning English as mapped on their two selves (Imposed and Public). The level of imposing on the part of "language teachers" and "families" on the learners was nearly the same and both had the same power. This showed that regarding present imposed identity indices, compared with others, these two categories had significantly more supremacies/concerns based on the learners' attitudes. As to future imposed self, among the four categories "the family members" had significantly the most influence on the learners compared to other factors. Comparing the two datasets for present vs. future selves could indicate that although for present condition of the learners, language teachers had more prominence over family members; this could also indicate that in the modern era and the more we go ahead in our life, the more family involvement and parent involvement becomes conspicuous in the community. However, documenting to the abovementioned statistics, nowadays, the parents' involvement has been so prominent in the pedagogical settings that the parents are regarded as the second chance of the students' learning. For the public self-status on four relational contexts it was evident that the mean for "family members" (parental involvement) and the "teacher" was significantly much more than the other two categories.

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